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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5856005>

INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Abstract: *This paper analyses the innovative and quite interesting methods we have in teaching English language. We may have a number of teaching methods in between traditional and modern. Everybody has their own understanding and conclusions on teaching English language. But this paper portrays combining this two types how we can make our teaching very effective. We have been completely bounded with traditional methods of teaching and understanding where the present day learners felt uncomfortable a bit. Learner's mind will never be static it is ever growing and ever changing. Whatever the teaching methodology can be, but teaching must be learner's centred.*

Key words: *teaching process, E-learning, e-mail, mobile devices, creative thinking, audio and visual materials, teamwork, humour, stimulation, engagement.*

Introduction: Essentially, the teaching process includes two main parts sending and receiving information. Eventually, a teacher tries his best to give knowledge as the way he understood it. The use of innovative methods in educational institutions has a powerful effect not only to improve education but also to empower learners. Trends have come in the field of education, and it affected the traditional system of education. Modern trends add vital role to the education sector in which the stress on quality over quantity. Traditional curriculum, class planning and old teaching routines help students to learn grammar and vocabulary for ages. One cannot deny that sometimes old methods of teaching makes learners get tired of memorising verbs, answering worksheets, and concentrating on repeating all the time. Though traditional methods such as audio - lingual and direct methods still offer useful results, yet they are clearly outdated in modern classroom. For sure social media and the internet as a whole have changed the way people learn languages in a positive way, it is imperative for modern language teachers to address the needs and interests of nowadays students. One can conclude that it is important for teachers to know the goals, needs and objectives of the learners in order set the suitable method for teaching. Grammar, vocabulary and language skills are vehicles to master the language and to reach the final outcomes. Accordingly, it is important for teachers to know their learners' goals so as to avoid irrelevant programs.

How I could choose the suitable method?

If the students want to learn English for a specific purposes, like in their business or in their companies they need using English sometimes. In that case the teacher should put in mind that this class is a business English class, and they need certain vocabularies that suit their work. The teacher needs to listen to their problems and need to use a method suitable to the nature of their companies. Give the students different tasks and make the learners search for that topic and the different topics that concern their job should be discussed in their classes afterwards. A way helps to increase the vocabulary that is needed in their jobs, and to increase their ability in discussing and analysing general ideas concerning their work. In short, the method or approach should be based according to the need of the learners. At the end of their course, a project is to be delivered to their boss for approval; a strategy adds a positive feedback in their learning process. If the learners are still young or teenagers, oral activities should be added more to them, videos of real world and many relevant course content to their material. Tests are also important in such cases, and the difficulty of the exam and the activities depends on the level of the learners. As for Evaluation it is so important; for the criteria of grading must be clear, the learners depend on it which leads afterwards to their goals. Students are tired with rigid curriculum, that use the Grammar Translation Method in which communicative approach is applied and depending a lot on learning, courses and lectures; the need for a moulded ability to compete and survive in the global world is the demand nowadays. For this, one has to apply a new trend to suit the needs of the learners. Researchers based on their studies emphasis on the meaningful contextualised discourse. To encourage easy discourse, technology can be used. Using technology is considered a new trend in teaching which makes learners understand faster and easier. Enjoyment has to be added to teaching to make learning environment more effective to reach the goals specially in learning foreign language.

1. E – Learning: Web-based Learning: it is a recent way of learning from distance, in which this online education is based also on the four skills (listening, speaking, writing, and reading) but they can be on the web. Students prefer the e – learning and can communicate through using e-mails, blogs or chats because they are easy to learn, easy to use and well – designed. Using technology in a number of fields has been so successful and beneficial for teachers to reach some specific goals particularly in education and for those who are learning a foreign language. Technology is seen enjoyable in these days in every step in our lives and with technology barriers are reduced.

a) E-mail

E-mail is a communication tool which is being used before the existence of Internet, but now it is used by students to join e-mail and to communicate with their instructors. It is an excellent way for communicating, because it is easy and useful, especially with foreign contacts and teachers can mix e-mail based on activities into their curriculum. For example if we have a class of students meet weekly for a lecture, a few days before

the class meeting, the teacher sends an e-mail for each student mentioning about the essay they have to discuss and the student have to write something about it, in this way the students can prepare for the class ahead of time. Teachers can also send his students some emails to start to write compositions or essays in English and send back to their teacher, this skill improves writing and vocabulary skills.

b) Mobile Devices

Nowadays everything changed and developed even teaching. Mobile is included in the teaching process and it is considered one of those technological devices that a learner can depend on in giving electronic information and it really helps in gaining knowledge regardless of place and time. In mobiles E - Dictionaries applications can be helpful for learners to check word meanings and it's synonymous. This application serves learners as a study guide tool, to understand the concepts that can be exemplified using live images, videos and online quizzes. Another feature for this application is the instant feedback and students evaluations during the lesson which will help to improve their performance.

2. Creative thinking:

Stimulate learners for creative thinking and think critically by including playful games and visual exercises, such methods really excites the learner's minds and stimulate their interest in learning. A teacher should always encourage new ideas of his students; it is considered one of the best ways to develop creative ideas and to encourage their freedom in exploring the new language. Good quality innovation in education could make learners learn more in a shorter time and could stimulate learning proficiency. Therefore, it is important to create a good innovation in the teaching process. It is important to support an environment that can motivate learners in their learning process, create activities to solve the problems the learners face. Such a method depends a lot on teachers and how to apply the suitable activity and learning model and ask clever questions that creates creative thinking. The results discovered that the approaches which support the creation of creative and innovative education should focus on systematical progress. These approaches usually grounded on design-based learning, problem - solving, creative thinking, research writing learning, or innovative teaching process could lead to innovative education creatively.

3. Audio and Visual Materials:

Teachers should not depend on the students' imagination, but he should include audio – visual Materials to his courses to ensure that the idea is understood better. Depending on audio – visual materials will help the development of the listening, reading and comprehension skills of students. There are also a number of ideas like inviting native guests; to listen to the right way of pronouncing words, presentations, data show, seminars or even using charts or poster presentation. The teacher should not let this visual or audio material to skip his domination role, for these materials are only aiding his job but are not as a substitute for his role. It is an undeniable fact that audio - visual

was one of the operative ways in the past and in the present also; it enables students to practice what they have learned. It is really an effective way of teaching for learners can achieve communication by using gestures, eye contact and facial expression to convey meaning

4. Outside Classroom:

The environment really has a great effect on learners. Most of the best classes when they are outside the classroom; taking students outside the usual class refresh their ability and excitement in learning. Whatever is going to be given since is a change of routine is going to be remembered without much effort. This experience is considered as a field trip which helps to build experience for doing an assignment afterwards. The teacher should establish an objective for the event and connect it with the new environment, as the new location creates an inspiration, this will encourage the learner of the language to blend between the society and curriculum; students should make an assignment on the related topic. After the trip the learners can have a discussion in the class to connect what they have learned and highlighted the importance of such a trip.

5. Work Together As a Team:

Teamwork is defined “as a cooperative process that allows ordinary people to achieve extraordinary results” . As everyone knows, the result of every teamwork is always great and effective. Encouraging learners to do teamwork; one helps the other in their weak points to have a complete sharing project that each learner feels he is part of that afford. Maybe in a teamwork the teacher shares with his students the activity and all can be one great teamwork which is considered one of the best strategies in learning.

6. Humour:

It demands creativity and imagination to capture students’ attention and interest in one’s teaching. From students’ point of view, a repetitious lecture would delay their interest to focus in the class. So adding humour in the class is so useful and motivates students’ comprehension. There are benefits to include humour in the language classroom. Activities that can increase fun and learning by lowering students’ nervousness are shared. It is important to teach students while playing and laughing, that avoids unease and keeps the thread of learning with no stress especially when there is a lot of work to do or when it is a very long session

9. Stimulating Classroom Environment:

A well - decorated classroom is a good environment for students to stimulate the learner’s mind. It helps them to think better and encourage creative exploration. A positive environment for sure has a positive impact on its learners. Learners might bring the outside problems in the class like home problems or fear of tests or live pressure, which will lack their motivation and dulls the love of learning so using warm positive classroom really affects their learning ability and encourages them to ask questions and to be involved in the class lecture.

10.Engagement:

It is important for students to be engaged with the real world, making learners involved in everyday life makes learning language easier and memorable. Instead of conventional teaching methods, students were taken to visit local businesses where they were able to witness how the knowledge that they were learning applied to the real world. Multiple days were set aside for this practice and all students were required to wear business suits in order to attend. The idea is to get students engaged and to connect their learning to the real world. Engaging learners with the real world makes learning more meaningful for students and they become more aware of the choices they make in society.

Conclusion: At last, there is no fixed way or the best method of teaching, but there is a best teacher. A teacher can use the traditional or the trendy method or mix between the two depending on his class needs. Teaching is a complex art, the more methods the teacher has the better, to be able to use the right one in the right time. Whether using technology or not, the teacher is the master of the role of teaching and his way can be effective if he chooses the right method in the right place and time, and if he can solve the learners problems and serve the learners' needs.

References:

1. Bolliger, Doris U. (2018) Engagement Matters: Student Perceptions on the Importance of Engagement Strategies in the Online Learning Environment. Carolina: Charlotte University of Wyoming press
2. LeLoup, J. & Ponterio, R. (1997). Internet Technologies for Authentic Language
3. Shiyab, Said (ed.) (2009). Pedagogical Effect of Humor on Teaching. California: California State University press
4. Ur, Penny. (2009) A Course in Language Teaching: Practice and Theory. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
5. Wilhelm, Jeffrey D. (1997). "You Gotta BE the Book" in Teaching Engaged and Reflective Reading with Adolescents. New York: Teachers College.
6. Wu, Yanfang. (2005) A Comparative Study of Online Privacy Regulations in the U.S.